

SCIENTIFIC PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS OF EDUCATING STUDENTS IN A PATRIOTIC SPIRIT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15005937>

Abstract: Patriotic education develops the spirituality and social activity of students, forms love for their homeland, selflessness and a sense of responsibility. Education ensures the transmission of national values between generations.

Keywords: Love of the Motherland, education, patriotism, national values, civic spirituality

Introduction.

In the current conditions of globalization, it is becoming increasingly important to pay special attention to the spiritual and moral education of the younger generation, in particular, to the issue of educating them in the spirit of patriotism. The development and stability of each society directly depends on the high sense of patriotism of the younger generation. Therefore, in the process of education, one of the important directions of education is to form in students a sense of national pride, respect for their history, and loyalty to their country.

Patriotism is not only love for the Motherland and national values, but also a sense of responsibility for the development of society, selflessness in the interests of the Motherland. Therefore, there is an increasing need for scientific and pedagogical study of the process of educating students in the spirit of patriotism, and the development of effective methods and mechanisms. This article analyzes the pedagogical foundations of the formation of students' sense of patriotism, scientific mechanisms of the educational process, and practical experiences.

The purpose of the study is to scientifically analyze the process of educating students in the spirit of patriotism, substantiate pedagogical approaches, and develop effective methods. The study analyzes the pedagogical foundations of the formation of patriotism in the process of education and upbringing, advanced foreign experiences, and national values.

The same content is embodied in the hadith that has been passed down from ancestors to generations: "Loving the homeland is faith." If we look at our long history, we will witness that the feeling of faith in the homeland has been revered by our people since ancient times. We can learn about the actions of famous people who came from our ancestors, their efforts for the development

of the homeland, through their works and historical information that have come down to us. Educating students in the spirit of patriotism requires a systematic approach based on scientific pedagogical mechanisms. The decrees and resolutions issued by our government in recent years also directly serve to further develop this area. The fact that the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his congratulatory message to the participants of the international conference on "Current issues of studying and promoting Uzbek classical and modern literature at the international level," emphasized that "When literature, art and culture live, the nation and people, all of humanity live in peace" also indicates that paying attention to literature is an important social issue in the comprehensive education of our youth. The process of educating patriotism not only makes students feel it from the heart, but also forms in their minds a sense of love for their homeland, dedication and responsibility.

The word "education" is derived from the Arabic verb "robba" (ar. يَتَرَبَّأُ [تَرْبِيَاةً]) and means to raise, increase, take under control, guide and reform. Education is a practical pedagogical process aimed at forming certain physical, mental, moral, and spiritual qualities in a person; a set of measures taken to ensure that a person has the characteristics necessary for living in society. Education is the most ancient and eternal value that ensures human humanity. Without education, neither an individual nor a human society can exist. Because the values that ensure the existence of a person and society are passed on from one generation to another only thanks to education. Therefore, education, as a national value, is directly important in educating young people, including students, in the spirit of patriotism, instilling in their minds. The goal of patriotic education is to develop high social activity, civic responsibility, spirituality in society, strengthen the state, ensure its interests and development. The main features of educating students in the spirit of patriotism include the following aspects:

1. Teaching historical and cultural heritage: Introducing students to the historical, cultural and literary heritage of their people, introducing them to national values and traditions. This teaches young people to love and respect their country, language and culture.

2. Instilling love for the homeland: Explaining to students the need to love their homeland, work for its development and prosperity. It is important to show patriotism not only in words, but also in practical activities.

3. Forming a sense of service to the homeland: Explaining to students the responsibility of each person to serve their homeland, enhance its prestige and contribute to the development of society. This leads young people to spiritual perfection.

4. Training of personnel: Patriotism is not limited to artistic and verbal expressions, but includes the development of healthy spiritual and moral qualities in students. They should be ready to shape the future of the country, along with solid knowledge, moral values, physical and mental education.

5. Promoting peace and justice: Developing important values in students, such as peace-loving, justice and respect for human rights in international relations. Patriotism means not only loving one's country, but also a positive outlook on the whole world and humanity.

6. Raising virtuous and kind people: It is necessary to pay great attention to instilling in students human qualities in the spirit of patriotism, developing qualities such as kindness, conscientiousness, justice, cooperation and mutual respect. By properly directing patriotic education, students will be ready to support peace and stability not only in their own country, but also in the whole world.

Living with the fate of the nation, faith in the homeland, justice, and a sense of humanity were highly formed in the teachings of our great ancestors, who became our national pride and honor. We can see this in the activities of one of our truly patriotic compatriots, Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro. Sheikh Najmiddin Kubro encouraged young people to be kind to each other, while increasing their love for the homeland. The brave son of Khorezm, who took up a sword in his hand and dealt a crushing blow to the enemy in the cause of the freedom of his homeland, is Jaloliddin Manguberdi. Studying the life of Jaloliddin Manguberdi and his activities in the path of faith in the homeland based on a deep analysis is of great importance in shaping and improving the views of adolescent students on faith in the homeland, boundless love for the Motherland, pride and honor, sacrificing one's life for the sake of peace of the homeland and the people, and humanity. Throughout his life, Jaloliddin Manguberdi loved his people and homeland, highly valued its history and culture, and deeply felt and cherished the beauties of mother nature. According to legend, Jaloliddin slapped his brother on the forehead when he threw a piece of wood into the flowing Jayhuna, shouting - it is a great sin to throw a piece of wood into the water, spit on the ground, you see Khorezm in the place of your mother! – he exclaims. This narration shows that Jaloliddin Manguberdi had a high love and faith for his

homeland, his motherland. The above-mentioned behavior, manners, morals, and beautiful qualities characteristic of Jaloliddin's childhood serve as an example for the present and future generations. Promoting such qualities as his steadfastness, enlightenment, heartfelt love for the homeland, appreciation of his teachers, courage, and honesty, and showing that he is a model person for the younger generation in all respects, is one of the important tasks of teachers today. The main goal of educating students is to raise them to be pious and religious by thoroughly instilling the foundations of science in their minds, to cultivate a conscious approach to every event in social life, and to develop the ability to apply the acquired knowledge and skills in life. In this respect, literature lessons are also a means of educating the younger generation in the spirit of the lofty ideals that our society promotes.

Forms and methods of patriotic education should be aimed at the formation of active citizenship, feelings of love for the homeland, beloved Uzbekistan and their small corners. Such forms of civic-patriotic education include involving schoolchildren in independent research work in the disciplines of education and history. Participation in spiritual and educational events of the school, knowledge and taking a place in the preservation and protection of historical monuments are also important features

Conclusion:

Educating students in the spirit of patriotism is an important factor for the development of society and the stability of the nation. The results of the study show that patriotic education has a positive effect on the personal development of students, their understanding of national identity and social activity. Therefore, it is necessary to effectively use national values, historical traditions and modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

The following scientific and pedagogical mechanisms are of great importance for the effective organization of patriotic education:

- Systematic inclusion of patriotic themes in curricula;
- Formation of national consciousness of students through literature, art, music and cultural heritage;
- Organization of practical projects, historical expeditions and patriotic events;
- Strengthening patriotic education in cooperation with parents and society.

In conclusion, instilling in the younger generation the qualities of national pride, patriotism and selflessness is the general responsibility of not only the education system, but also society. Therefore, educational institutions, teachers

and parents should pay special attention to educating students in the spirit of love for the Motherland and loyalty to their people. This scientific article offers effective approaches and pedagogical mechanisms for the development of patriotic education and emphasizes the importance of continuing research in this area.

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